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**FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPLEMENTING EFFECTIVE
BUDGET POLICY IN UKRAINE**

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The Ukrainian economy is currently experiencing an unprecedented shock, the largest in its history, due to the full-scale military invasion by the Russian Federation, which has significantly affected all aspects of the country's economic system. There has been a decline in the production of key goods that form the basis of Ukraine's export potential. The engineering, logistical and social infrastructure of regions and cities are being destroyed, and the outflow of professionals abroad or their partial relocation is temporarily excluding millions of people from active economic life.

Consistent military victories on the front lines and sustainable post-war reconstruction are only possible with a stable economic situation, that is why attention is focused on the domestic economy and budgetary system, which determine Ukraine's ability to successfully recover after the end of the conflict.

There are many examples in world history of countries recovering after military action. Since the end of World War II, there have been more than 30 major wars and over 250 military conflicts involving at least 60 countries.

However, not all countries have had successful experiences of reconstruction. In the case of Ukraine, the situation is considered unique, as the presence of developed economic potential, legitimate authority, state institutions and a stable financial system distinguish its prospects from other countries that have faced military conflicts. Thus, compared to some European and Eastern countries after 1945 and to this day, Ukraine appears unique [1, p. 240].

Budget implementation is an important stage of the budgetary process, which determines the degree of effectiveness of the performance by public authorities of the functions and powers assigned to them. The implementation of the budget is carried

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out by the state budget, the budget of the local government bodies and the budget of the state specialized funds [2, p. 62].

To create a Ukrainian ‘Marshall Plan’ aimed at improving the functioning of the budgetary system, it is necessary to consider the experience of countries such as Poland, Israel, Georgia, Western Germany and Japan. These countries not only suffered the most during the war but also achieved economic development thanks to effective policies.

In Poland, after World War II and under communist rule, the country's economy found it difficult to integrate into the global market. Hyperinflation arose due to a large budget deficit, which was filled with issuing money. To quickly revamp the management system, global economists created a reform plan that included stuff like a law on financial savings in state-owned companies, limits on bank financing of deficits, getting rid of preferential lending, uniform tax rules, and more. These decisions helped get stabilization loans to restructure Polish businesses. By introducing strict budgetary restrictions, state-owned enterprises spent only the funds they earned, which halted inflation and put Poland on the path to economic recovery. The experience of Poland's reconstruction became a striking example of the successful application of ‘shock therapy,’ which consists of the rapid and widespread implementation of systemic economic reforms, including the budgetary system [3, p. 23].

Many areas of Israel suffered serious damage as a result of the ‘war of independence.’ The country's economy was under great pressure due to the massive influx of 800,000 immigrants from Arab countries. Defence spending accounted for more than 40% of the country's total expenditure. Agriculture also suffered, covering only half of the food needs. Export revenues covered less than 30% of import costs.

During the wars with Arab countries, when Israel was establishing its independence, it was necessary to find additional resources. These resources included ‘independence loans’ or government bonds placed in other countries. International aid, such as loans and grants from the United States, was also important. Israel became the

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first country to allow the United States to place its bonds for post-war reconstruction.

After the war, Israel implemented a series of reforms in the budget system aimed at economic recovery, financial stabilization and financial sustainability. These reforms included optimization of defense spending, restructuring of budget programs, attracting investment and tax reforms. The similarity between Israel and Ukraine is that both countries have hostile neighbors and, during both wartime and peacetime, are forced to allocate significant funds to defense and the military sector.

The Georgian government's main step in improving local budgets was to grant them broader powers and autonomy. To improve interaction between local self-government bodies and the central government, changes were made to the budget process. The main goal was to give local governments more power and allocate additional financial resources for the implementation of state programs that required the participation of local authorities. The surplus in local budgets contributed to the strengthening of the country's economy [4, p. 283].

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